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EDITORIAL

Holiness - A Transformative Encounter with the Divine, Other, and World

Holiness, often associated with a deep sense of sacredness and the other, can be a transformative life experience. Many religious traditions emphasize the journey towards holiness as a path of spiritual growth and personal transformation. It is important to note that holiness and its transformative effects can vary widely across different belief systems. Some may find holiness within the framework of organized religion, while others may experience it through personal spirituality, practice of mindfulness, or other forms of transcendent experiences. Ultimately, the transformative power of holiness lies in its ability to elevate individuals beyond the mundane and connect them to a deeper, more profound dimension of existence. This transformative process may involve letting go of ego-driven desires, attachments, and negative patterns of thought and behaviour. A transformative experience of holiness often leads to increased gratitude and appreciation for life. Pursuing holiness involves aligning one's life with higher values and principles. This alignment can lead to a more meaningful and purposeful existence, with individuals making choices that reflect their commitment to the sacred and the divine. As individuals undergo a transformative experience toward holiness, they may become more understanding and compassionate toward others, fostering a sense of unity and interconnectedness.

Encountering the Divine is often considered a central aspect of holiness in many religious and spiritual traditions. This

encounter is a profound and transformative experience that transcends the ordinary and connects individuals with the sacred. It includes a heightened awareness of the Divine presence, where the individual feels a deep and intimate connection with a transcendent reality. It may manifest as a sense of God's presence amid daily life, in nature, or during moments of prayer and contemplation.

In encountering the 'other,' holiness expands the traditional understanding of holiness beyond a solitary, mystical experience with the Divine to encompass the recognition of the sacred in our relationships with others. This recognition implies a belief that each individual carries a spark of the divine, and encounters with others become opportunities to connect with this higher aspect. By recognizing the sacred in others, individuals may feel a deep sense of interconnectedness and a desire to understand and alleviate the suffering of those whom they encounter. It involves recognizing the divine image in others, regardless of differences in background, beliefs, or circumstances. Engaging with others in a way that is considered holy often includes acts of service and altruism. By selflessly helping others, individuals express a commitment to the well-being of the 'other' as an expression of their reverence for the sacred in every person. An enhanced relationship with others becomes an avenue for spiritual growth and self-discovery. In encountering the 'other,' holiness challenges individuals to transcend superficial differences and connect on a deeper, spiritual level. This transcendent understanding fosters unity and harmony among diverse individuals.

Living 'holiness in the world' involves recognizing the sacred and transcendent aspects of the broader existence beyond individual or interpersonal encounters. This perspective views the entire world - nature, events, and day-to-day life - as infused with a divine presence. Living 'holiness in the world' requires a mindful awareness of the present moment. It involves being fully present and attuned to the richness and sacredness inherent in the simple

experiences of daily life. Recognizing holiness in the world may lead to a commitment to ethical and responsible engagement with the environment and other living beings. This perspective emphasizes stewardship and care for the earth as sacred. Encountering holiness in the world often fosters a deep sense of gratitude and reverence for the gift of life. It encourages individuals to appreciate and cherish the sacredness inherent in all aspects of existence. Encountering holiness in the world may involve recognizing meaningful coincidences or synchronicities that suggest a more profound, divine order in unfolding events and experiences.

Seeking holiness in the world emphasizes going beyond personal piety to encompass a transformative engagement with society's social, economic, and environmental challenges. It involves a commitment to social justice and equity, advocating for fair distribution of resources, addressing systemic inequalities, and working towards a society where all individuals can thrive. It involves the ability to understand and share in the experiences of others, particularly those who are marginalized or facing injustice. It comprises building and nurturing communities of solidarity. It includes fostering connections among people, encouraging collaboration, and recognizing the importance of collective efforts in addressing societal challenges. It involves resolving conflicts, promoting dialogue, and fostering reconciliation within communities and societies. It emphasizes the inherent dignity of every human being, advocating for human rights, combating discrimination, and promoting a culture of respect and inclusivity. It recognizes the interconnectedness of personal spirituality and societal well-being, fostering a commitment to the divine and the welfare of the broader human family. In short, living holiness in the world involves a holistic and transformative approach that integrates spiritual values into actions and initiatives to create a more just, compassionate, and equitable society.

Pope Francis, in his Apostolic Exhortation *Gaudete et Exsultate* explores the theme of holiness in the contemporary world, offering reflections and guidance on how individuals can pursue a path of holiness amid the challenges of modern life. Holiness, for Pope Francis, involves a personal encounter with Christ. He speaks about the transformative power of encountering Jesus and emphasizes that true holiness comes from a relationship with the living God. He reiterates the universal call to holiness, emphasizing that holiness is not reserved for a select few but is a vocation for everyone. He encourages each person, regardless of their state of life, to pursue holiness with joy and enthusiasm. He heartens us to maintain a sense of joy, even in the face of difficulties, and to avoid becoming overly serious or self-absorbed in our spiritual journey. He encourages us to be joyful witnesses of the Gospel, reflecting the love and mercy of Christ in their lives.

Pope Francis believes that holiness is found in daily life. When done with love and a sense of service, ordinary activities become opportunities for encountering God and growing in holiness. He highlights the importance of small gestures of love and kindness in pursuing holiness. He contends that these seemingly insignificant actions, done with love, contribute to building a more just and compassionate society. He emphasizes the relevance of the Beatitudes from the Sermon on the Mount as a guide to holiness and Christian living. He sees the Beatitudes as a blueprint for holiness, calling us to embody humility, meekness, mercy, peacemaking, and a thirst for justice. He often emphasizes the importance of mercy and compassion as essential components of holiness. According to Pope Francis, holiness involves a commitment to social justice and a special concern for the poor and marginalized. He notes that a person's relationship with God is inseparable from their relationship with others, and authentic holiness includes a commitment to social justice and solidarity with those in need.

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